

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>**Research Article****FREQUENCY OF PATIENTS PRESENTING WITH
OBESITY-HYPOVENTILATION (PICKWICKIAN) SYNDROME AT A
TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL**Rashid Ahmed Khan^{1*}, Muhammad Iqbal², Nasrullah Aamir³,Hamid Nawaz Ali Memon⁴, Aatir H. Rajput⁵ and Muhammad Muneeb⁶¹Department of Pulmonology - Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences, Jamshoro²Department of Medicine – Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences, Jamshoro³Department of Medicine. Peoples University of Medical & Health Sciences, Nawabshah⁴Zulekha Hospital Dubai, United Arab Emirates⁵Sir Cowasjee Jehangir Institute of Psychiatry, Hyderabad⁶Indus Medical College, Tando Muhamaad Khan**Abstract:**

Background: Obesity, around the world, is becoming more and more common. With greater prevalence, more of the mal-effects have begun to manifest, among which obesity-hypoventilation syndrome is the most under-rated, seldom-recognized and mostly un-diagnosed condition, despite its serious impact on the quality of life of an individual. **Objective:** This research hopes to study the frequency of obesity-hypoventilation (pickwickian) syndrome among patients presenting at a tertiary care hospital. **Methodology:** The study was carried out on patients presenting at department of pulmonology (chest medicine) at Liaquat University Hospital from June 2016 to June 2017. The data was collected using a structured interview based questionnaire and relevant investigations after taking written informed consent and all necessary measures were employed to ensure anonymity of the data subjects. The data obtained was analyzed using Microsoft Excel 2016 and SPSS v. 21.0. The frequency of patients was analyzed and its trends studied against gender, sociodemographic variations and time of the year. **Results:** 13 male and 12 female patients presented with obesity-hypoventilation syndrome in the designated study duration. Among the total 25 patients, 1 patient belonged to the lower economic class, 7 belonged to the middle economic class and 17 patients belonged to upper economic class. Most patients presented during the winter months and least during the summer months. The mean BMI of the subjects stood at 31 kg/m² and the mean age was recorded to be 54 years. **Conclusion:** After careful consideration, the results make it abundantly clear that, patients with obesity-hypoventilation syndrome scarcely, but do present at tertiary care hospitals at our settings. What is worrisome however, is that with the predicted increase in obesity, the frequency of patients may rise and thus healthcare professionals should practice vigilantly and advise appropriate investigations, especially arterial blood gasses whenever the disease is suspected in obese patients.

Keywords: Obesity, Hypoventilation, Pickwickian Syndrome, Hypercapnia and Hypoxemia.

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Please cite this article in press as Rashid Ahmed Khan *et al.*, **Frequency of Patients Presenting with Obesity-Hypoventilation (Pickwickian) Syndrome at a Tertiary Care Hospital**, *Indo Am. J. P. Sci.*, 2017; 4(12).

INTRODUCTION:

Obesity is becoming a major medical concern in several parts of the world, [1] with huge economic impacts on health-care systems, [2] resulting mainly from increased cardiovascular risks. [3] At the same time, obesity leads to a number of other mal-effects, among which obesity-hypoventilation syndrome is the most under-rated, seldom-recognized and mostly un-diagnosed condition, [4] despite its serious impact on the quality of life of an individual. [5] The condition also leads to increased morbidity and mortality. [6] Obesity hypoventilation syndrome is distinct from other sleep-related breathing disorders [7] although overlap may exist. [8] Obesity hypoventilation syndrome patients may have obstructive sleep apnea/hypopnea [9] with hypercapnia [10] and sleep hypoventilation, [11] or an isolated sleep hypoventilation. [12]

The World Health Organization (WHO) defines “overweight” as a body mass index (BMI) equal to or more than 25kg/m², and “obesity” as a BMI equal to or more than 30kg/m². Obesity is further classified into 3 classes — class 1 obesity (BMI, 30-34.9 kg/m²); class 2 obesity (BMI, 35-39.9 kg/m²) and class 3 obesity (BMI, ≥40kg/m²), with increasing morbidity in proportion to increasing BMI. The organization estimates that by year 2015, around 2.3 billion adults will be overweight and more than 700 million will be obese.

The interaction between obesity and respiratory system is not straightforward, as one affects the other via several mechanisms. [13] Excessive fat accumulation over the chest and abdomen adversely affects lung respiratory system mechanics, [14] leading to physiological derangement and functional impairment, which can be reversed in some subjects following weight loss. [15] Of note is the point that the distribution of body fat seems to be more important than total body fat and BMI per se. [16, 17] Obesity leads to reduction in chest wall compliance

and respiratory muscle endurance with increased airway and chest wall resistance. [18] In addition, there will be loss of expiratory reserve volume accompanied in cases of morbid obesity, with reduction in total lung capacity and functional residual capacity. [19-25] Obesity hypoventilation syndrome is defined as the combined presence of obesity (BMI,>30kg/m²) with awake arterial hypercapnia (PaCO₂>45mmHg) in the absence of other causes of hypoventilation. [26]

As stated earlier, despite its major impact on health, this disorder is under-recognized and under-diagnosed. Available management options include aggressive weight reduction, oxygen therapy and using positive airway pressure techniques. This research hopes to study the frequency of obesity-hypoventilation (pickwickian) syndrome among patients presenting at a tertiary care hospital.

METHODOLOGY:

The study was carried out on patients presenting at department of pulmonology (chest medicine) at Liaquat University Hospital from June 2016 to June 2017. The data was collected using a structured interview based questionnaire and relevant investigations after taking written informed consent and all necessary measures were employed to ensure anonymity of the data subjects. The data obtained was analyzed using Microsoft Excel 2016 and SPSS v. 21.0. The frequency of patients was analyzed and its trends studied against gender, sociodemographic variations and time of the year. Diagnosis was based on the patient’s arterial blood gasses result and the level of hypercapnia and hypoxemia.

RESULTS:

The mean BMI of the subjects stood at 31 kg/m² and the mean age was recorded to be 54 years. 13 male and 12 female patients presented with obesity-hypoventilation syndrome in the designated study duration.

Among the total 25 patients, 1 patient belonged to the lower economic class, 7 belonged to the middle economic class and 17 patients belonged to upper economic class.

Most patients presented during the winter months and least during the summer months. The graph below presents the trend in more detail.

DISCUSSION:

The exact prevalence of OHS in the general population remains unknown, and most prevalence data describe subjects with obstructive sleep apnea, wherein its prevalence has been estimated to range from 10% to 38% in different groups. [27-31] Nowbar and colleagues reported the prevalence of OHS among hospitalized adult patients with a BMI > 35kg/m² to be 31% after ruling out other causes of hypercapnia. [32]

Additionally, OHS patients were reported to be heavy users of health-care resources. Berg et al. reported OHS patients to have higher health-care utilization several years prior to evaluation and treatment of their sleep breathing disorder. [33] There was a substantial reduction in “the number of days of

hospitalization” once the diagnosis was made and treatment instituted. [34]

The classic presentation is an obese middle-aged male (usually BMI, $\geq 35\text{kg/m}^2$) with excessive daytime sleepiness and neurocognitive function impairment. Due to the simultaneous occurrence of obstructive sleep apnea in the majority of patients, symptoms like snoring, witnessed apneas and poor sleep quality with early morning headache and reduced performance are reported

Clinical examination confirms the high BMI and might display signs of cor-pulmonale and secondary pulmonary hypertension. Measuring oxygen saturation noninvasively by pulse oxymetry reveals reduced SpO₂. An arterial blood gas taken when

breathing room air confirms the presence of low PaO₂, PaCO₂ and a high bicarbonate level, signifying the chronic nature of the process. [15, 32] Blood tests include complete blood count to rule out secondary erythrocytosis, and thyroid function test to rule out severe hypothyroidism.

Despite our best efforts, we could not find any literature till-date that checked the individual frequency of obesity hypoventilation among different genders, socioeconomic classes. Neither could we unearth any evidence regarding the individual frequencies of presentation of patients presenting with obesity hypoventilation syndrome during different months of the year.

CONCLUSION:

After careful consideration, the results make it abundantly clear that, patients with obesity-hypoventilation syndrome scarcely, but do present at tertiary care hospitals at our settings. What is worrisome however, is that with the predicted increase in obesity, the frequency of patients may rise and thus healthcare professionals should practice vigilantly and advise appropriate investigations, especially arterial blood gasses whenever the disease is suspected in obese patients.

REFERENCES:

1. Aserinsky E, Kleitman N. Two types of ocular motility occurring in sleep. *J Appl Physiol*. 1955;8:1–10. [PubMed]
2. Sinton CM, McCarley RW. Neurophysiological mechanisms of sleep and wakefulness: A question of balance. *Semin Neurol*. 2004;24:211–23. [PubMed]
3. Eldridge FL. Central nervous system and chemoreceptor factors in control of breathing. *Chest*. 1978;73:256–8. [PubMed]
4. Lahiri S, Mokashi A, Delaney RG, Fishman AP. Arterial PO₂ and PCO₂ stimulus threshold for carotid chemoreceptors and breathing. *Respir Physiol*. 1978;34:359–75. [PubMed]
5. O'Regan RG, Majcherczyk S. Role of peripheral chemoreceptors and central chemosensitivity in the regulation of respiration and circulation. *J Exp Biol*. 1982;100:23–40. [PubMed]
6. Dempsey JA, Smith CA, Harms CA, Chow C, Saupé KW. Sleep-induced breathing instability: University of Wisconsin-Madison Sleep and respiration Research Group. *Sleep*. 1996;19:236–47. [PubMed]
7. Douglas NJ, White DP, Pickett CK, Weil JV, Zwillich CW. Respiration during sleep in normal man. *Thorax*. 1982;37:840–4. [PMC free article] [PubMed]
8. Krieger J. Breathing during sleep in normal subjects. *Clin Chest Med*. 1985;6:577–94. [PubMed]
9. Ancoli-Israel S, Kripke DF, Mason W. Characteristics of obstructive and central sleep apnea in the elderly: An interim report. *Biol Psychiatry*. 1987;22:741–50. [PubMed]
10. Hoch CC, Reynolds CF, 3rd, Monk TH, Buysse DJ, Yeager AL, Houck PR, et al. Comparison of sleep-disordered breathing among healthy elderly in the seventh, eighth, and ninth decades of life. *Sleep*. 1990;13:502–11. [PubMed]
11. Kreis P, Kripke DF, Ancoli-Israel S. Sleep apnea: A prospective study. *West J Med*. 1983;139:171–3. [PMC free article] [PubMed]
12. Young T, Palta M, Dempsey J, Skatrud J, Weber S, Badr S. The occurrence of sleep-disordered breathing among middle-aged adults. *N Engl J Med*. 1993;328:1230–5. [PubMed]
13. Punjabi NM. The epidemiology of adult obstructive sleep apnea. *Proc Am Thorac Soc*. 2008;5:136–43. [PMC free article] [PubMed]
14. World Health Organization: Obesity. [cited on 2008 Oct 30]. (Updated periodically throughout the year). Available from: <http://www.who.int/topics/obesity/en/>
15. Hakala K, Stenius-Aarniala B, Sovijarvi A. Effects of weight loss on peak flow variability, airways obstruction, and lung volumes in obese patients with asthma. *Chest*. 2000;118:1315–21. [PubMed]
16. Collins LC, Hoberty PD, Walker JF, Fletcher EC, Peiris AN. The effect of body fat distribution on pulmonary function tests. *Chest*. 1995;107:1298–302. [PubMed]
17. Pischon T, Boeing H, Hoffmann K, Bergmann M, Schulze M, Overvad K, et al. General and abdominal adiposity and risk of death in Europe. *N Engl J Med*. 2008;359:2105–20. [PubMed]
18. Ladosky W, Botelho MA, Albuquerque JP., Jr. Chest mechanics in morbidly obese non-hypoventilated patients. *Respir Med*. 2001;95:281–6. [PubMed]
19. Jones RL, Nzekwu MM. The effects of body mass index on lung volumes. *Chest*. 2006;130:827–33. [PubMed]
20. Teixeira CA, Dos Santos JE, Silva GA, de Souza ES, Martinez JA. Prevalence of and the potential pathophysiological mechanisms involved in dyspnea in individuals with class II or III obesity. *J Bras Pneumol*. 2007;33:28–35. [PubMed]
21. Zerah F, Harf A, Perlemuter L, Lorino H, Lorino AM, Atlan G. Effects of obesity on respiratory resistance. *Chest*. 1993;103:1470–6. [PubMed]
22. Koenig SM. Pulmonary complications of obesity. *Am J Med Sci*. 2001;321:249–79. [PubMed]
23. Mokhlesi B, Tulaimat A, Faibussowitsch I, Wang Y, Evans AT. Obesity hypoventilation syndrome: Prevalence and predictors in patients with obstructive

- sleep apnea. *Sleep Breath.* 2007;11:117–24. [PubMed]
24. BaHammam A. Positive airway pressure therapy and daytime hypercapnia in patients with sleep-disordered breathing. *Chest.* 2008;134:218–9. [PubMed]
25. Olson AL, Zwillich C. The obesity hypoventilation syndrome. *Am J Med.* 2005;118:948–56. [PubMed]
26. The Report of an American Academy of Sleep Medicine Task Force. Sleep-related breathing disorders in adults: Recommendations for syndrome definition and measurement techniques in clinical research. *Sleep.* 1999;22:667–89. [PubMed]
27. Akashiba T, Akahoshi T, Kawahara S, Uematsu A, Katsura K, Sakurai S, et al. Clinical characteristics of obesity-hypoventilation syndrome in Japan: A multicenter study. *Intern Med.* 2006;45:1121–5. [PubMed]
28. Kessler R, Chaouat A, Schinkewitch P, Faller M, Casel S, Krieger J, et al. The obesity-hypoventilation syndrome revisited: A prospective study of 34 consecutive cases. *Chest.* 2001;120:369–76. [PubMed]
29. Laaban JP, Chailleux E. Daytime hypercapnia in adult patients with obstructive sleep apnea syndrome in France, before initiating nocturnal nasal continuous positive airway pressure therapy. *Chest.* 2005;127:710–5. [PubMed]
30. Resta O, Bonfitto P, Sabato R, De Pergola G, Barbaro MP. Prevalence of obstructive sleep apnoea in a sample of obese women: Effect of menopause. *Diabetes Nutr Metab.* 2004;17:296–303. [PubMed]
31. Verin E, Tardif C, Pasquis P. Prevalence of daytime hypercapnia or hypoxia in patients with OSAS and normal lung function. *Respir Med.* 2001;95:693–6. [PubMed]
32. Nowbar S, Burkart KM, Gonzales R, Fedorowicz A, Gozansky WS, Gaudio JC, et al. Obesity-associated hypoventilation in hospitalized patients: Prevalence, effects, and outcome. *Am J Med.* 2004;116:1–7. [PubMed]
33. Berg G, Delaive K, Manfreda J, Walld R, Kryger MH. The use of health-care resources in obesity-hypoventilation syndrome. *Chest.* 2001;120:377–83. [PubMed]
34. Mokhlesi B, Kryger MH, Grunstein RR. Assessment and management of patients with obesity hypoventilation syndrome. *Proc Am Thorac Soc.* 2008;5:218–25. [PMC free article] [PubMed].